

Contents lists available at [ScienceDirect](https://www.sciencedirect.com)

Science of the Total Environment

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/scitotenv

A high-resolution monitoring approach of urban CO₂ fluxes. Part 1 - bottom-up model development

Stavros Stagakis*, Christian Feigenwinter, Roland Vogt, Markus Kalberer

Department of Environmental Sciences, University of Basel, Klingelbergstrasse 27, 4056 Basel, Switzerland

HIGHLIGHTS

- Monitoring urban CO₂ flux is needed to assess the progress towards climate neutrality.
- A new model of anthropogenic CO₂ emissions and biogenic CO₂ fluxes is developed.
- The highly dynamic spatiotemporal variability of the urban CO₂ fluxes is demonstrated.
- The model is designed for direct comparison with in-situ atmospheric observations.
- Modelled anthropogenic emissions are comparable to a local inventory.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

ARTICLE INFO

Editor: Anastasia Paschalidou

Keywords:

Carbon dioxide
Greenhouse gas
Climate change
Anthropogenic emissions
Biogenic flux
Fossil fuels

ABSTRACT

Monitoring carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions of urban areas is increasingly important to assess the progress towards the Paris Agreement goals for climate neutrality. Cities are currently voluntarily developing their local inventories, however, the approaches used across different cities are not systematically assessed, present consistency issues, neglect the biogenic fluxes and have restricted spatial and temporal resolution. In order to assess the accuracy of the urban emission inventories and provide information which is useful for planning local climate change mitigation actions, high resolution modelling approaches combined or evaluated with atmospheric observations are needed. This study presents a new high-resolution bottom-up (BU) model which provides hourly maps of all major components contributing to the local urban surface CO₂ flux (i.e. building emissions, traffic emissions, human respiration, soil respiration, plant respiration, plant photosynthetic uptake) and can therefore be used for direct comparison with in-situ atmospheric observations and development of local scale atmospheric inversion methodologies. The model design aims to be simple and flexible using inputs that are available in most cities, facilitating transferability to different locations. The inputs are primarily based on open geospatial datasets, census information, road traffic monitoring and basic meteorological parameters. The model is applied on the city centre of Basel, Switzerland, for the year 2018 and the results are compared to a local inventory. It is demonstrated that the model captures the highly dynamic spatiotemporal variability of the urban CO₂ fluxes according to main environmental drivers, population activity dynamics and geospatial information proxies. The annual modelled emissions from buildings and traffic are estimated 14.8 % and 9 % lower than the respective information derived by the local inventory. The differences are mainly attributed to the emissions from the industrial areas and the highways which are beyond the geographical coverage of the model.

* Corresponding author at: Atmospheric Sciences, Department of Environmental Sciences, University of Basel, Klingelbergstrasse 27, 4056 Basel, Switzerland.

E-mail addresses: stavros.stagakis@unibas.ch (S. Stagakis), christian.feigenwinter@unibas.ch (C. Feigenwinter), roland.vogt@unibas.ch (R. Vogt), markus.kalberer@unibas.ch (M. Kalberer).<https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.160216>

Received 25 July 2022; Received in revised form 13 October 2022; Accepted 12 November 2022

Available online xxx

0048-9697/© 2022 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

Urban areas account for over 55 % (4.2 billion) of the world population (UN, 2019) and approximately 67–72 % of the global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (IPCC, 2022). At the same time, there is a strong urbanization trend, indicating that urban areas will continue to expand and host 68 % (6.7 billion) of the world population by 2050 (UN, 2019). The key role of urban areas in climate change mitigation is increasingly realized and local authorities around the world show clear ambition in taking action, developing climate action plans and pledging very ambitious GHG emission mitigation goals (e.g. C-40, 2022; EC, 2022; Global Covenant of Mayors, 2022; ICLEI, 2022). In accordance to the Paris Agreement (UNFCCC, 2015), cities have started to develop their local GHG emission inventories to establish baselines, define their reduction targets and monitor their progress, often following one of the publicly available protocols (e.g. GHG Protocol, 2021; GCoM CRF, 2018). The methodologies for cities are generally aligned to the IPCC guidelines for national inventories, following the bottom-up (BU) activity data and emission factor approach (e.g. IPCC, 2006).

Nevertheless, cities' inventories are still developed voluntarily in support to the national commitments and there is no systematic and peer-reviewed assessment of their quality or accuracy (Gurney et al., 2021). The inventories are produced with annual time resolutions and usually do not account for the highly dynamic spatial or temporal distribution of emission sources and sinks, providing often a mixture of the traditional emission scopes (i.e. Scope 1: all emissions within the local geographical boundary, Scope 2: emissions driven by the consumption of electricity, Scope 3: emissions driven by the consumption of materials, goods, and services) (Chen et al., 2019). These attributes limit the usefulness of these datasets for urban planning of mitigation actions, where fine spatio-temporal scales are meaningful for urban design decisions (neighborhood, block, or building scale, e.g. Chrysoulakis et al., 2013), and prevent the direct comparison to atmospheric observations, which is the only current means to independently evaluate emission estimates and provide associated uncertainties (CO₂ Blue Report, 2015). Moreover, the development of such annual inventory datasets is usually a slow process with months or years of delay and therefore cannot be used for fast (course-correcting) decision-making processes.

During the last decade, significant progress has been made in advancing the traditional BU inventory approaches with increased spatial and temporal information, but the research so far has focused mainly on continental scales to complement the official national inventories submitted to UNFCCC with consistent and observation-based information (e.g. Friedlingstein et al., 2020; Gurney et al., 2020; Janssens-Maenhout et al., 2019; Oda et al., 2018). Such applications do not reach the required level of detail to characterize the CO₂ source/sink variability across urban landscapes. However, there are some recent studies and projects that focus on high resolution quantification of urban CO₂ fluxes. The Hestia Project (Gurney et al., 2012), limited to U.S. cities, is a pioneer initiative of quantifying fossil fuel CO₂ emissions at building and road segment scales and hourly resolution. Hestia is essentially a downscaled version of the Vulcan Project, which integrates multiple datasets of different origin, spatial and temporal resolution, such as national CO emissions reporting, direct flux measurements and traffic monitoring (Gurney et al., 2020, 2009). The Hestia product has been also used to support high-resolution atmospheric inversion modelling applications where the BU emission estimations are constrained by in-situ atmospheric observations of CO₂ mixing ratios (Lauvaux et al., 2016).

There are also recent developments of BU models which combine detailed geographical datasets with meteorological data, emission factors and population activity data to simulate high spatial and temporal resolution urban CO₂ and other pollutant emissions. The High-Resolute Resolution Modelling Emission System (HERMES, Guevara et al., 2013) is an atmospheric modelling emission framework which has been recently enhanced with a BU module to compute high-resolution urban anthropogenic emissions of multiple pollutants and from different sectors (Guevara et al., 2020). Moreover, the Surface Urban Energy and Water balance Scheme (SUEWS, Järvi et al., 2011) is an urban land surface model which simulates

urban energy exchanges and has been recently advanced to compute CO₂ fluxes from both anthropogenic and biogenic sources (Järvi et al., 2019).

Accounting for the biogenic components within the urban CO₂ flux is an important addition to the urban BU models, which is often neglected (Gurney et al., 2017). Photosynthesis and respiration from vegetation and soil can significantly modify the urban CO₂ flux, especially during spring and summer (Bellucco et al., 2017; Decina et al., 2016; Hardiman et al., 2017; Järvi et al., 2019; Menzer and McFadden, 2017; Velasco et al., 2016; Ward et al., 2013; Weissert et al., 2016; Winbourne et al., 2022). Specifically, previous studies found that even though on daily to annual scales biogenic uptake cannot totally offset urban emissions, vegetation is able to temporarily take up roughly the same amount of emitted CO₂ during summer afternoons in an area of Washington DC/Baltimore (Winbourne et al., 2022), while on the other hand soil respiration is potentially enhanced in urban areas and contribute significantly to the urban emissions (Decina et al., 2016). In applications where BU flux estimations are combined with observations, it is essential that the biogenic contribution is considered. Moreover, urban inventories can benefit from this information to optimise urban planning decisions towards reaching net-zero targets (Decina et al., 2016; Winbourne et al., 2022). Biogenic components in urban areas present complex behaviour related to the local environment, are usually under intense site-specific management and are extremely inhomogeneous and patchy. Therefore, the urban biogenic CO₂ fluxes are difficult to model using the existing tools (Hardiman et al., 2017). In addition to the biogenic components, human respiration, which can be classified as either anthropogenic or biogenic process, is an important parameter that modifies the urban CO₂ flux and ought to be accounted for in applications involving observation-based estimations (Gurney et al., 2017). Human respiration can account even up to 39 % of the local urban CO₂ flux when building emissions are negligible (Järvi et al., 2019).

Despite the recent advances in urban BU modelling methodologies, more research is needed for developing accurate, efficient and widely applicable tools for understanding and monitoring the heterogeneous and complex CO₂ flux processes across the urban landscapes. Integrated methods focussed on all components contributing to the local scale CO₂ fluxes and providing the capability of combining BU models with atmospheric observations in data assimilation schemes are still lacking from the literature. This paper describes a new BU framework to model all local urban CO₂ flux components in hourly time steps and at high spatial resolution. The approach targets to describe the total actual surface flux, comparable to hourly urban eddy covariance observations (Part 2, Stagakis et al., 2022), and provides a method for independent and consistent quantification of urban emissions. The model considers building and vehicle emissions, human, plant and soil respiration, and photosynthesis. Industrial emissions from large power plants are not considered in this version of the model. The model targets to be simple and flexible, using inputs that are available in most cities, and that can be easily transferred to different locations. The application of the model in the city centre of Basel, Switzerland, is demonstrated and the outcomes are compared to the official city inventory of 2018, which is the most recent at the time being.

2. Site and data description

2.1. Study area

The study area is the city centre of Basel, Switzerland (Fig. 1). Basel is a central European city located in the north-western corner of Switzerland at the border to Germany and France. The Canton of Basel (Basel-Stadt), covers an area of 37.0 km² with a total population of 200,256 residents according to 2018 census. According to the official energy statistics for the Canton of Basel (Energistatistik Basel-Stadt, 2020), the main GHG emission sectors are industry, trade and services (46 %), residential emissions (35 %) and traffic (19 %). The study area size is 3,040 m (horizontal) x 2,980 m (vertical) and contains diverse land use types and urban structures.

At the centre of the study area lies the old city centre which is densely built with midrise buildings, restricted vehicle traffic and only few green

Fig. 1. Land cover map of the study area at 1 m resolution. The map is projected in UTM 32N (EPSG: 32632).

areas. The river Rhine is crossing the city centre coming from the E and then headed towards N. The old city centre serves today a mix of business, commercial and residential uses. Around the city core, the main land use features include the main business districts to the S – SE and E – NE of the centre, the University and University hospital buildings to the N – NW of the centre and the residential areas that extend mainly to the whole west part (NW – W – SW), the NE and SE of the study area. The main industrial districts of the city, as well as the airport, are located outside the study area. The majority of the study area can be characterized as LCZ-2: compact mid-rise, and only few locations at the SE and NW could be characterized as LCZ-5: open mid-rise, according to the Local Climate Zone (LCZ) Scheme of Stewart and Oke (2012).

Vehicle traffic is strictly regulated across the study area, with only few big traffic-oriented main roads (10,000–20,000 vehicles/24 h). The majority of the roads can be categorized as low traffic settlement roads (1000–5000 vehicles/24 h), while many areas are under traffic restrictions, called Tempo 30 (maximum speed of 30 km/h) and meeting zones (maximum speed of 20 km/h). An underground highway passes through the north part of the study area (not shown in Fig. 1), however the emissions originating from the traffic of this part are not considered at the current version of the traffic model.

2.2. Land cover

A Land Cover map (including land-use types) of the study area at 1 m resolution is produced combining multiple sources of information. The main source is the official survey map of Basel-Stadt of 2019 (Amtliche Vermessung Basel-Stadt, 2021), which serves as the base map for all additional information. The original 21 classification types

of the survey map were aggregated into 6 broad categories (i.e. buildings, roads, pavements, paved surfaces, soil/vegetation, water) which provide a good representation of the urban CO₂ sources and sinks. The information of tree crowns is then treated as an additional level of overlying information based on the data of the airborne LiDAR campaign of 2018 (Section 2.3). An overview of the land cover type fractions and the most abundant tree species in the study area is provided in Tables S.1 and S.2.

The buildings are further categorized as pure residential, partly residential (i.e. mix of residential and workplace), workplaces and commercial/industrial according to Basel-Stadt map of building types (Gebäudeadressen und -informationen, 2022) and the Urban Atlas (GMES/Copernicus land monitoring services, 2018). The commercial/industrial class is assigned to the buildings that are located inside the respective Urban Atlas polygons, classified by the Basel-Stadt building type map as partly residential (defined as 50 % commercial/industrial) and workplace (defined as 100 % commercial/industrial). Special buildings are further identified using Basel-Stadt Geodata (Schulstandorte - Gemeinde Basel, 2021) and OpenStreetMap (OpenStreetMap, 2021), i.e. schools, university buildings, hospitals and hotels.

The road type classification of the city authorities (Strassen und Wege, 2022) and the vehicle traffic zones (Verkehrsberuhigte Zonen, 2022) are used to derive a street classification scheme that is meaningful for vehicle emission modelling. Traffic-oriented roads inside the study area are classified as main roads and collecting roads. Settlement-oriented roads are usually under special restrictions and therefore are classified as settlement roads (no special restriction), Tempo 30 (30 km/h limit) and meeting zones (20 km/h limit). The rest of the roads are restricted to motor vehicles and classified as pedestrian roads.

2.3. Digital surface models (DSMs)

The urban morphology of the study area is characterized combining three surface-object models. The Digital Terrain Model (DTM) describes the elevation (m above sea level) of the ground, ignoring any object (e.g. buildings or trees) and is used with a 1 m resolution ([Terrainmodell - DTM, 2022](#)). The building heights (m above ground) are produced using the 3D model of the city, provided in vector format ([3D-Stadtmodell, 2021](#)). The latest product describes the building status of the year 2015. The vector containing the height information is transformed to a raster grid of 1 m resolution using the ArcGIS Software (ESRI). The tree heights (m above ground) are estimated using an aerial LiDAR dataset acquired in summer 2018. The pre-processed and classified (LAS V1.2 scheme, LIS Pro 3D, LASERDATA GmbH) LiDAR point cloud was post-processed using the LAStools software suite (Rapiddasso GmbH) to generate vegetation canopy maximum and minimum height at 1 m resolution. Digital Surface Models (DSMs) for buildings, trees and their combination are produced by adding the respective height products on the DTM. When adding both elements on the DTM to represent the full DSM, the higher element is kept for the pixels where buildings and trees overlap.

2.4. Leaf area index (LAI)

Copernicus Sentinel-2 (S2) imagery is used for the monitoring of urban vegetation LAI. S2 mission provides revisit time of 5 days using a constellation of two identical satellites S2A and S2B. The Level 2A (L2A) product by the Theia Land Data Centre of CNES (Centre national d'études spatiales) is used, which provides georeferenced and orthorectified surface reflectance (SR), water vapor content (WVC), aerosol optical thickness (AOT), cloud and geophysical masks, processed by the MAJA atmospheric processing software ([Hagolle et al., 2017](#)). S2 L2A imagery covering our study area is downloaded using the "theia_download" algorithm ([theia_download algorithm, 2021](#)). The 10 m SR bands in red (SR_{red} : 665 nm) and near-infrared (SR_{NIR} : 842 nm) are used to compute NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index) as $(SR_{NIR} - SR_{red}) / (SR_{NIR} + SR_{red})$ and the product is masked for clouds, cloud shadows and snow according to the L2A product flags. NDVI is converted to LAI values by applying an empirical exponential formula ([Stagakis et al., 2015](#)) and is then resampled from 10 m to 5 m resolution, enhancing the initial LAI values, using the vegetation fraction derived by the 1 m Land Cover products at 10 m ($\lambda_{v,10m}$) and 5 m ($\lambda_{v,5m}$) grids as:

$$LAI_{5m} = LAI_{10m} \cdot \frac{\lambda_{v,5m}}{\lambda_{v,10m}} \quad (1)$$

For Eq. (1) to be applicable, $\lambda_{v,10m}$ and LAI_{10m} are first resampled to 5 m without changing their initial values (i.e. 2×2 neighbouring pixels of the same value). Eq. (1) works when $\lambda_{v,10m}$ is not zero, thus in areas where vegetation fraction is zero, LAI_{5m} is also set to zero. The produced LAI imagery (5-day interval at optimum conditions) is then temporally linearly interpolated on a pixel by pixel basis to produce daily gap-filled imagery. In order to reduce the random noise on the timeseries, a moving 15-day maximum value composite filter is applied per pixel to the daily LAI timeseries.

The typical structure of tree canopies within urban canyons in the study area is two continuous rows of overlapping crowns with width of 7–12 m. Underneath the tree canopy is mostly impervious cover (i.e. paved, roads). The vegetation structures in parks, gardens and other open areas is mainly individual tree crowns or small tree patches (e.g. 30 m \times 30 m) over grass fields. Mixed pixel effects are expected in the LAI estimation method, especially in urban canyons, which would potentially induce some bias in the estimated values. A model sensitivity analysis to the uncertainty of LAI and other key inputs are provided in the Supplementary material (Fig. S.10, Table S.11).

2.5. Meteorological data

Table S.3 summarizes the station locations and the respective input meteorological variables that are used in this study, as well as the instrumentation used for each measurement. Air temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) and vapor pressure (kPa) are measured on a micrometeorological tower located near the centre of the study area and are considered uniform across the site. Vapor Pressure Deficit (VPD, kPa) is then calculated based on saturated vapor pressure estimation ([Buck, 1981](#)). Direct and diffuse incoming radiation are measured with a 2-axis sun tracker (INTRA, BRUSAG) at the roof-level in an unobscured location next to the micrometeorological tower. Measured shortwave radiant flux densities (W m^{-2}) are converted to photon flux densities ($\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) within PAR (i.e. photosynthetic active radiation, solar shortwave radiation between 400 and 700 nm) using the conversion factor suggested by [MacKerron \(2005\)](#). Soil temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) and volumetric water content ($\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$) are continuously measured at three different locations of the study area at 10 cm below surface. The locations have different characteristics, BKLI is at a street canyon, BKFP is at a non-irrigated park location and BSMP is at an irrigated park location.

2.6. Population density

Annual statistics per city block on residential population (by age group) and workplace employees ([Beschäftigte und Arbeitsstätten, 2021](#); [Wohnbevölkerung, 2021](#)) are used to derive maps of annual night-time and daytime building-scale population density (inhabitants per m^2 or inh. m^{-2}) for weekdays and weekends. The spatial resampling of the population is based on the assumption of proportionality between building inhabitants and building volume (estimated as *mean building height* \times *building plan area*, derived by land cover and DSM products). Considering the building type (i.e. residential, partly residential, workplace), building volume is separated to residential volume (V_{res}) and workplace volume (V_{wor}), so that population is redistributed between night-time, daytime, workdays and weekends.

Night-time building population density ($P_{n,b}$) is considered the same for weekdays and weekends and is estimated per building by scaling total block resident population (P_B) according to building volume as:

$$P_{n,b} = \left(P_B \cdot \frac{V_{res,b}}{V_{res,B}} \right) / A_b \quad (2)$$

$V_{res,b}$ is the building residential volume, $V_{res,B}$ is the block residential volume (the sum of all building residential volume per block) and A_b is the building plan area.

Weekday daytime building population density ($P_{d,b}$) is estimated by involving the distribution of block population by age, to calculate the inhabitants that stay home during day, and the number of employees per block (M_B), to calculate the population that occupy the working places, as:

$$P_{d,b} = \left(0.85 \cdot M_B \cdot \frac{V_{wor,b}}{V_{wor,B}} + P_{B,64} \cdot \frac{V_{res,b}}{V_{res,B}} + 0.35 \cdot P_{B,20} \cdot \frac{V_{res,b}}{V_{res,B}} \right) / A_b \quad (3)$$

$V_{wor,b}$ is the building workplace volume and $V_{wor,B}$ is the block workplace volume (the sum of all building workplace volume per block), $P_{B,64}$ and $P_{B,20}$ are block residents of the age classes over 64 and 20–64 respectively. The first part of Eq. (3) reflects the fact that workplaces are never occupied by the total number of their registered employees at the same time ([Järvi et al., 2019](#)), assuming a standard rate of 15 % employee absence. The second and third part estimate the population that stays home during weekdays according to the official statistics of Basel-Stadt on employment by age group ([Wohnbevölkerung nach Alter und Arbeitspensum, 2022](#)). The factor 0.35 on age class 20–64 reflects the sum of unemployed or inactive population (20 %) and the 15 % of the employees that are assumed to stay home. These assumptions produce $P_{d,b}$ maps with around 70,000–80,000 more people than $P_{n,b}$, which agrees with the official statistics regarding the incoming working population from other cantons and

countries (Beschäftigte und Arbeitsstätten, 2021; Grenzgänger nach Geschlecht und Wohnsitzstaat, 2022).

Weekend daytime building population density ($P_{e,b}$) is estimated as:

$$P_{e,b} = \left(0.5 \cdot M_B \cdot \frac{V_{wor,b}}{V_{wor,B}} + (P_B - 0.5 \cdot P_{B,20}) \cdot \frac{V_{res,b}}{V_{res,B}} \right) / A_b \quad (4)$$

The factor 0.5 indicates the assumption that 50 % of the employees from the age class 20–64 would go for work during weekends.

Special building types (i.e. schools, university, hospitals, hotels) are treated separately regarding the estimation of building population density. The equations and special assumptions for the population dynamics in these buildings are described in the Supplementary material.

2.7. Traffic data

Traffic counts per hour and vehicle type are available online for 31 locations across the city (Verkehrszähldaten motorisierter Individualverkehr, 2022). Most of the traffic stations operated by the Basel-Stadt are located on main and collecting roads (Fig. S.1, Table S.4). Settlement-oriented roads (i.e. settlement, Tempo-30 and meeting areas) are not efficiently monitored by permanent traffic counters. To overcome this measurement gap, the available data from short-term surveys in Basel-Stadt since 2010 (Verkehrszähldaten, 2022) were used to extract annual diurnal profiles (weekend and weekday) from all the available surveys according to road types. This analysis provided strong linear relationships (Fig. S.2) between main road hourly traffic and the hourly traffic of settlement-oriented road types. These relationships are used to estimate the hourly traffic of each vehicle type in these roads assuming that the vehicle type mix is the same with the main roads excluding only the heavy duty vehicles and the busses.

3. Model description

3.1. Building emissions

The model distinguishes two types of emissions: i) the emissions related to space heating (E_B), and ii) the emissions from commercial/industrial buildings due to their increased energy demand (E_C). The first category concerns all inhabited buildings in the study area, irrespectively of their use (i.e. residential, workplaces and commercial/industrial), while the second category of emissions is on top of the space heating emissions for the buildings classified as commercial/industrial only.

E_B is modelled by estimating the energy needed for space heating per building volume according to air temperature (T_{air}) and then converting it to the CO₂ emission equivalent using emission factors (EFs) for the fuels used in the area of interest. T_{air} is converted to Heating Degree Hours (HDH), defined in this approach as the difference between the hourly mean T_{air} and a base temperature ($T_{base} = 20$ °C, following Lietzke et al., 2015). HDH is zero when hourly T_{air} is over 20 °C and when the mean T_{air} of the last 24 h is over 15 °C. The equation for hourly E_B estimation in $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ is expressed as:

$$E_B = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{f(HDH) \cdot f_i \cdot EF_i \cdot H_B \cdot B_o}{3600} \quad (5)$$

$f(HDH)$ is the function to estimate energy consumption for space heating per building volume (W m^{-3}) according to HDH. f_i and EF_i are the fraction and the emission factor of the fuel i used in the local energy fuel mix for heating, H_B is the building height (m), B_o is a Boolean value indicating if the building is inhabited ($P_{d,b} > 1$) and 3600 converts $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$ to $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The EFs for the two main fuels used in the study area are shown in Table 1, while the fuel mix for heating is spatially variable (Fig. S.4). $f(HDH)$ is expected to be site-specific according to building characteristics and can be derived according to local energy usage statistics. In this study we have derived a non-linear function using monthly

Table 1

Emission factors for the fuels used by buildings (Kantonaler Richtplan Teilrichtplan Energie, 2020) and for the vehicle types aggregated for emission categories (i.e. hot and cold emission factors) and fuel type (i.e. gasoline and diesel vehicles) (HBEFA 4.1, 2021).

	Emission factor (EF)
Building heating fuels	$\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ Wh}^{-1}$
Natural gas	5480.6
Heating oil	6707.6
Vehicle types	$\text{g CO}_2 \text{ veh}^{-1} \text{ km}^{-1}$
Motorcycle	109.3
Passenger car	182.5
Light duty vehicle/light commercial vehicle	258.7
Heavy duty vehicle	833.3
Urban bus/coach	938.3

data of HDH and residential building energy consumption from the period 2005–2020 for the Canton of Basel:

$$f(HDH) = 0.295 + 0.24 \cdot HDH + 0.004 \cdot HDH^2 \quad (6)$$

The methodology to derive Eq. (6) is described in the Supplementary material. The model for space heating emissions based on Eq. (5) is applied on all building types, assuming the same main pattern of energy consumption for space heating irrespectively of building use.

However, buildings classified as commercial/industrial are known to have much higher energy demand than other buildings (Kantonaler Richtplan Teilrichtplan Energie, 2020) and this extra energy consumption is assumed to follow a diurnal and weekday pattern according to working hours. Hourly values of commercial/industrial emissions (E_C) in $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ are calculated as:

$$E_C = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{W \cdot C_h \cdot C_f \cdot f_i \cdot EF_i \cdot H_B \cdot B_o}{3600} \quad (7)$$

W is the hourly energy consumption for commercial/industrial processes per building volume (in W m^{-3}), C_h is a workhour coefficient (0–1) for workdays and C_f is the fraction of the building volume occupied for industrial/commercial use. C_h is represented by a Gaussian-type curve to describe the diurnal pattern of commercial/industrial emission magnitude during a workday, with peak ($C_h = 1$) at local midday and half ($C_h = 0.5$) at 06:00 and 18:00 (local time). Outside working hours (20:00–06:00) and during weekends, C_h is zero. W is expected to vary depending on the type of commercial/industrial process of each building, therefore, it is very hard to realistically predict W variability in space and time. For model simplicity, we assume a standard W value for all commercial/industrial buildings of the study area (7 W m^{-3}), estimated as the difference between the total energy consumption of heating oil, district heating and natural gas according to city statistics (Energienstatistik Basel-Stadt, 2020; Fig. S.5) and the energy consumption for heating estimated using Eq. (6), for the whole Canton and the year 2018. Only natural gas is considered as a fuel for commercial/industrial processes in the present application.

The spatial resolution of the building emission model is defined by the resolution of the building DSM and land cover map. The present application uses the 1 m resolution products as inputs and resamples the E_B and E_C outputs to 20 m.

3.2. Traffic emissions

Vehicle CO₂ emissions are modelled based on the hourly traffic station data across the city and the road type classification (Fig. 1). Main and collecting roads are separated in several segments according to the main road junctions. The other road types are considered uniform (i.e. each road type represents one segment). Road segments equipped with a traffic station are attributed with the hourly measured vehicle count data, while

the rest are attributed with the mean hourly count of all stations of the specific road type, assuming homogeneous spatial profiles for each road class. The equation to estimate hourly traffic emissions in $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at individual road segments across the study area is the following:

$$E_{V(S)} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{V_i \cdot EF_i \cdot D_S}{A_S \cdot 1000 \cdot 36000 \cdot 44.01 \cdot 10^{-6}} \quad (8)$$

V_i and EF_i are the vehicle number and the emission factor i of the specific vehicle type, D_S is the length of the road segment in meters and A_S is the area in m^2 of the road segment (including adjacent paved surfaces within the street canyon). The EFs and vehicle types used in this study are shown in Table 1. D_S and A_S are estimated based on the land cover product, which defines the model resolution. The original 1 m input resolution is used, but the $E_{V(S)}$ products are resampled to 20 m. The coefficient 1000 is used for transforming the EFs from g/km to g/m , 3600 converts h^{-1} to s^{-1} and $44,01 \cdot 10^{-6}$ converts g CO_2 to $\mu\text{mol CO}_2$. Hourly $E_{V(S)}$ is represented as a spatially uniform value across the area of the respective segment (S), assuming that CO_2 is well mixed within the urban canyon. The spatial mosaic of all $E_{V(S)}$ across the study area constitutes the hourly E_V . This version of the model does not account for the traffic on an underground highway which crosses through the North part of the study area.

3.3. Human respiration

The CO_2 emitted by the human respiration (R_H) is modelled according to building and street population density dynamics by converting population densities (inh. m^{-2}) to R_H ($\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) with a standard per capita respiration emission rate $201.54 \mu\text{mol inh.}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (Moriwaki and Kanda, 2004). Hourly building population density is derived from the yearly night-time ($P_{n,b}$), weekday daytime ($P_{d,b}$), weekend daytime ($P_{e,b}$) population density maps and the traffic station data, following the approximations:

$$P_{d,b,h} = TI \cdot P_{d,b} + (1 - TI) \cdot P_{n,b} \quad (9)$$

$$P_{e,b,h} = TI \cdot P_{e,b} + (1 - TI) \cdot P_{n,b} \quad (10)$$

$$TI = \min \left[\frac{(\bar{V} + \bar{N})}{1000}, 1 \right] \quad (11)$$

$P_{d,b,h}$ and $P_{e,b,h}$ are the hourly building population density during weekdays and weekends respectively. TI is a traffic index derived by the sum of mean hourly vehicle (\bar{V}) and pedestrian (\bar{N}) counts of all traffic stations in the study area. The denominator 1000 in Eq. (11) is set empirically to a near-maximum value of the equation numerator. The approach assumes that diurnal building population density dynamics and street traffic are co-varying, so during night-time when TI is near zero, $P_{d,b,h}$ and $P_{e,b,h}$ are close to the night-time population density, whereas during day when TI is close to 1, they are close to the daytime population density. Such dynamic representation of building density according to a traffic index captures holidays or other cases of unexpected and unusual population distributions.

Street population density is estimated according to pedestrian traffic counts as:

$$P_{s,h} = N / (1.3 \cdot 3600 \cdot 10) \quad (12)$$

where, N is the hourly pedestrian counts per lane, interpolated spatially at 1 m resolution across the streets and paved surfaces of the study area using a triangulation-based natural neighbour method (MATLAB griddata, 2022), 1.3 is the average walking pace of a pedestrian in m s^{-1} , 3600 converts m s^{-1} to m h^{-1} and 10 is a representative value in meters for an average street canyon width for single lane streets in the study area. Eq. (12) estimates the pedestrian density at the street canyons assuming a standard average walking pace and equal distances between pedestrians on an hourly average. Population densities are calculated at 1 m resolution, but the final R_H maps are resampled to 20 m.

3.4. Biogenic fluxes

The biogenic flux components are modelled using a semi-empirical approach based on the main environmental controlling parameters and considering urban morphology effects. Plant photosynthesis (P_V) is modelled by dividing the urban canopy into multiple horizontal layers (n) and simulating the plant photosynthesis of each layer using a custom directional radiation interception algorithm and standard environmental control equations. Plant respiration (R_V) and soil respiration (R_S) are modelled according to empirical functions related to air temperature (T_{air}), soil temperature (T_{soil}) and soil moisture (θ). CO_2 fluxes over water bodies, such as the river (Fig. 1), are assumed zero. All models run at 5 m resolution providing gridded flux products (x,y subscripts are omitted in the following equations for simplicity) which are resampled to 20 m. The overall algorithm can be summarized in the following equations:

$$P_V = \sum_{i=1}^n \left[LAI_{sun,i} \cdot A_o \cdot \left(1 - e^{-\frac{a \cdot PAR_{sun,i}}{A_o}} \right) + LAI_{shade,i} \cdot A_o \cdot \left(1 - e^{-\frac{a \cdot PAR_{shade,i}}{A_o}} \right) \right] \quad (13)$$

$$A_o = A_{max} \cdot f(T_{air}) \cdot f(VPD, \theta) \quad (14)$$

$$R_V = LAI \cdot D_{sc} \cdot R_l \quad (15)$$

$$R_S = \lambda_s \cdot R_{S,ref} \cdot \exp \left[E_o \cdot \left(\frac{1}{T_{ref,S} - T_0} - \frac{1}{T_{soil} - T_0} \right) \right] \cdot \left[\frac{(\theta - \theta_0)^b}{(\theta_{ref} - \theta_0)^b} \right] \quad (16)$$

$LAI_{sun,i}$ and $PAR_{sun,i}$ are the fraction of LAI which receives direct radiation and the respective PAR (total) on the horizontal layer i . Accordingly, $LAI_{shade,i}$ and $PAR_{shade,i}$ are the fraction of LAI which does not receive any direct radiation and the PAR (i.e. sum of diffused, scattered and reflected) on this LAI fraction at the horizontal layer i . The radiation components (i.e. direct, diffuse, scattered, reflected) and the LAI fractions that receive them are estimated hourly based on the Beer-Lambert principles of radiation interception through the canopy (Campbell and Norman, 1998), modified for the urban environment to consider building shading, diffuse radiation reduction within urban canyons, reflected radiation by urban surroundings and radiation interception from surrounding tree crowns (Appendix A). A_{max} and A_o represent the leaf gross photosynthetic rates at saturated PAR at optimum conditions and after environmental controls respectively, while the terms in the parentheses of Eq. (13) describe the nonrectangular hyperbolic photosynthesis dependence on light, with a being the quantum yield for CO_2 assimilation (Appendix B). Temperature effects on photosynthesis $f(T_{air})$ (Eq. (14)) are modelled according to the empirical peaked function by June et al. (2004) and the effects of atmospheric humidity and soil moisture deficits combined $f(VPD, \theta)$ (Eq. (14)) are modelled based on Leuning's equation on stomatal conductance (Leuning, 1995), adding an empirical reduction factor to simulate θ constraints (Appendix B). R_V (Eq. (15)) is modelled based on an exponential fixed- Q_{10} equation for leaf respiration (R_l) (Appendix B) and a daylight scalar D_{sc} which takes the value of 1 during night and 0.5 during day, assuming a 50 % inhibition of dark respiration during day for all species (e.g. Atkin et al., 2000; Brooks and Farquhar, 1985; Peisker and Apel, 2001; Villar et al., 1995).

Eq. (16) is a modified Arrhenius equation for R_S estimation based on Lloyd and Taylor (1994). λ_s is the soil fraction at 5 m resolution according to the Land Cover product, $R_{S,ref}$ is a reference R_S at a reference $T_{soil} = 10^\circ \text{C}$, E_o is a temperature sensitivity parameter, $T_{ref,S}$ is the reference temperature and T_0 is the low-temperature limit for respiration. Soil moisture dependence is incorporated by adding the last term of Eq. (16), which is an empirical function based on a low soil moisture limit (θ_0), a reference soil moisture (θ_{ref}) and an empirical coefficient b (Liss et al., 2009). The biogenic flux model is parametrised based on literature values for temperate deciduous broadleaved trees and grasses, which are the main plant types in the study area. The constant values used in the biogenic models as well as the respective literature references are summarized in Table S.5.

In Eqs. (14) and (16), θ is considered spatially variable according to irrigation patterns. Parks (including sport areas) are regularly irrigated during dry periods by the city green management authority. On the contrary, street trees, alleys and smaller public green areas are not irrigated. Therefore, park areas (according to the Land Cover map) are assigned with the average θ measured in BKFP and BSMP (parks) and the rest of the area is assigned to the θ measured at BKLI (street alley).

4. Model performance

4.1. Temporal variability

The model ran for the year 2018 at hourly time step. Fig. 2 presents the daily variability of input meteorological data, LAI and the flux model outputs which are affected by meteorology (i.e. building and biogenic emissions). It is obvious that temperature is a major controlling factor for building emissions and biogenic fluxes. At the same time, PAR daily variability has clear effects on photosynthesis. During winter, the building emissions are high (Fig. 2c), fluctuating between 10 and 20 $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ on daily average across the study area. During very cold periods, where daily air temperature falls below zero, building emissions exceed 20 $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. During winter, the biogenic fluxes are low due to low temperature, PAR and LAI values (Fig. 2a, b). Spring conditions are favourable for photosynthesis and at the same time building emissions decrease below 10 $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (Fig. 2c). LAI reaches maximum in spring, θ is still high (Fig. 2b) and temperature is at optimal levels for photosynthesis. Nevertheless, the spring photosynthetic peak ($\sim 4 \mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) is still lower than the sum of the building emissions and respiration components at the same period ($\sim 8 \mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$). Towards

summer, even though no space heating is required in buildings, their emissions are not zero due to E_C which presents a weekday pattern (Fig. 2c). 2018 was an exceptionally dry year. It is interesting that LAI decreases already from July along with θ , both reaching very low values during August, staying low until the end of October (Fig. 2b). These conditions drove photosynthesis and respiration to lower levels, gradually decreasing already from July on and reaching near-zero values by the end of October (Fig. 2c). It is important to note that the range of y-axes of Fig. 2c is different for building and biogenic fluxes (by a factor of 5) in order to be visible and comparable, demonstrating that biogenic flux dynamics in the study area are hardly comparable to the anthropogenic emissions.

The temporal dynamics of traffic and human respiration emissions are best described in diurnal patterns for different day types (Fig. 3). These variables show intense diurnal variability, with no important pattern changes across the year, except during holiday seasons where the traffic tends to decrease. Fig. 3 demonstrates how traffic (E_V) and human respiration (R_H) emissions are affected by the mean diurnal traffic patterns. E_V follows very closely the traffic patterns (Fig. 3a), with lower emissions during weekends and the typical emission peaks every morning and afternoon rush-hours during weekdays (Fig. 3b). After midnight close to zero E_V rises again early in the morning to reach maximum values around 5–6 $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (mean of the whole study area). The numbers of heavy-duty vehicles and busses (Fig. 3a) are higher during morning and lower during afternoon during weekdays, but still remain a small fraction of the total vehicles in the study area. Weekend E_V diurnal pattern does not show a morning peak and tends to reach maximum in late afternoon (Fig. 3b). R_H is also partly following the traffic patterns, however, the variability is not so intense as E_V . Night-time and weekend R_H is around 2 $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and during workhours it rises slightly above 2.5 $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$

Fig. 2. Time-series of daily average (a) air temperature (T_{air}), soil temperature (T_{soil}), global photosynthetically active radiation (PAR), (b) soil volumetric water content (SVWC, θ), vapor pressure deficit (VPD), leaf area index (LAI), precipitation, (c) building emissions ($E_B + E_C$), soil respiration (R_S), plant respiration (R_V) and plant photosynthesis (P_V) for the year 2018. θ , LAI, $E_B + E_C$, R_S , R_V and P_V are expressed as the mean of the study area. Y-axis scaling in (c) is different for building (left axis) and biogenic fluxes (right axis).

Fig. 3. (a) Diurnal hourly mean weekday and weekend profiles for vehicle counts during 2018. The total vehicle counts per lane across all available stations on main and collecting roads of the Canton are used. Line thickness for each hour represents the number of heavy-duty vehicles and urban busses/coaches. (b) Diurnal hourly mean weekday and weekend profiles for traffic emissions (E_V) and human respiration emissions (R_H). E_V and R_H are expressed as the mean of the study area. The shaded area of each curve (a and b) is the 25th–75th percentile range.

$m^{-2} s^{-1}$ due to the inflow of people to the city centre. Two slight humps appear in the temporal profile of weekday R_H during the morning and evening rush hours (Fig. 3b), which are possibly the side effect of using traffic counts in estimating the hourly population densities (Eqs. (9)–(11)).

Detailed seasonal and daily flux patterns for all model components are presented in the Supplementary material (Figs. S.8, S.9), where the overall contribution of each component to the net F_C can be examined. It is interesting to note that building emissions ($E_B + E_C$) dominate the total fluxes across the study area, especially during winter. Moreover, an important aspect of the modelled fluxes is how the biogenic components contribute to the urban CO_2 flux. Their influence is considerable during summer and especially during daytime hours, when photosynthesis offsets nearly 1/3 of the daytime emissions during weekdays and about 1/2 of the daytime emissions during weekends (Fig. S.9c, d).

4.2. Spatial variability

The spatial variability of emissions captured by the model along with the main geospatial inputs are represented in Figs. 4 and 5. Building and human respiration emission patterns show interesting and somewhat contrasting spatial patterns (Fig. 4c, d). Annual building emissions peak in the city centre and the commercial/industrial buildings (Fig. 4c), while human respiration is higher in the residential neighbourhoods with exceptions of some very highly frequented buildings, such as the University hospital (Fig. 4d). The city centre has higher buildings (Fig. 4a) and higher building density than the residential neighbourhoods, concentrating more population during workhours (Fig. 4b). However, this pattern does not affect significantly the annual human respiration emissions (Fig. 4d), which is mainly defined by the night-time population patterns. Some districts of the study area have distinguishable lower building emissions than others (Fig. 4c) due to the district heating coverage which decreases the local emissions (Fig. S.4).

Main and collecting roads have the greatest share in the annual traffic emissions with considerable variability between the different road segments within the study area (Fig. 5a, c). The differences between road segments of the same road type reflect the effects of the actual traffic count measurements assigned to some road segments. It is distinguishable that main road segments around the railway station (south part of the study area) present much higher total emissions than other main roads (Fig. 5c). Annual net biogenic flux ($R_s + R_V - P_V$) shows an interesting patchy spatial pattern across the study area, with some areas acting as sinks and others acting as sources of CO_2 (Fig. 5d). The general pattern shows that open green areas (e.g. parks, sports areas) tend to act as sinks, whereas

street alleys and gardens around buildings (i.e. low sky view factors) tend to act as sources (Fig. 5d). Another parameter towards this pattern would also be that parks are irrigated during summer dry periods while the rest of the public green areas are not. The model does not take into account possible irrigation in private gardens.

4.3. Comparison with the city inventory

The annual total CO_2 emissions per model component for the study area are listed in Table 2. Buildings have the greatest share of emissions, contributing 60 % to the total CO_2 balance. Even though traffic emissions can be very high in some road segments (Fig. 5c), the total contribution to the total study area is much lower than the building emissions (23.5 %), while human respiration contributes significantly to the total budget (18 %). Photosynthesis has also a significant share in reducing the emitted CO_2 (10.4 %), but when considering plant/soil respiration in the annual scale, the biogenic balance reduces the anthropogenic emissions only by 1.6 %. The contributions of the different components vary according to seasons (Figs. S.8, S.9).

The model results are compared to the official inventory statistics for the Canton of Basel for the year 2018 (Energietatistik Basel-Stadt, 2020). To be comparable, only the statistics for the building energy consumption which produces local CO_2 emissions is considered (i.e. natural gas and heating oil). Energy supplied to the buildings through district heating and electricity is not taken into account because the respective emissions occur outside the study area. For traffic, the total vehicle fuel (i.e. gasoline, diesel) consumption statistics are taken into account. The conversion to CO_2 equivalent follows the EFs used by the local authorities (Kantonaler Richtplan Teilrichtplan Energie, 2020). The annual total emissions expressed in different units are presented in Table 3. Due to the difference in the area covered by the model and the inventory, it is difficult to make direct comparison. If the building emissions are expressed per square meter of land, the modelled emissions are much higher than the inventory (Table 3), however, the building volume included in the study area is also much higher than the Cantonal average. Therefore, when the building emissions are expressed per cubic meter of building, the model results are comparable to the inventory (14.8 % difference). The inventory provides higher building emission estimation, which can be explained by the fact that the fraction (per volume) of commercial/industrial buildings (higher energy demand) inside the study area ($0.14 m^3 m^{-3}$) is less than the entire Canton ($0.19 m^3 m^{-3}$) and due to the higher emissions of commercial buildings, this could explain the observed difference.

Fig. 4. Maps of the (a) building height in 1 m resolution (polygons indicate the commercial/industrial buildings, hospital is the large building near the centre of the study area on the west side of the river), (b) building inhabitants during weekdays, (c) total building emissions for 2018 ($E_B + E_C$, $\text{kg CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ a}^{-1}$) in 20 m resolution and (d) total human respiration emissions for 2018 (R_H , $\text{kg CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ a}^{-1}$) in 20 m resolution. All maps are projected in UTM 32N (EPSG: 32632).

Traffic emissions are extremely spatially variable according to the traffic conditions as demonstrated in Fig. 5c. When comparing total traffic emissions from different areas, the road lengths within the areas are a better indicator than expressing the emissions per land area. As shown in Table 3, the modelled traffic emissions are lower than the inventory. This was expected since emissions from highways are not considered in the current version of the model. Highways in the Canton of Basel concentrate around five times the average main road traffic, in the order of 30,000–80,000 vehicles/24 h, according to the data of the Swiss Federal Roads Office (FEDRO). The inventory provides the estimated traffic emissions according to a traffic model for the Canton of Basel-Stadt emissions (Energistatistik Basel-Stadt, 2020) considering all the road types of the Canton. In an attempt for a better comparison between the two models and areas of interest, the FEDRO annual traffic data from a station in the underground

highway that crosses the north part of the study area were used to estimate the total traffic emissions for 2018 within this highway segment according to Eq. (8). The results are shown in Table 3 in parentheses, demonstrating that highways are the main traffic emission sources within the Canton and the modelled data are comparable to the inventory (9.0 % difference). This argument is supported also by the Hestia high resolution urban inventory (Gurney et al., 2012), where it is demonstrated that for the Marion County, Indiana, interstate and arterial roads comprise 15 % of the total road length but 62 % of total traffic CO_2 emissions.

4.4. Comparison with other models

Only a small number of other recent studies have performed similar comprehensive emissions estimates for cities in Europe and North

Fig. 5. Maps of the (a) road types in 1 m resolution, (b) mean summertime leaf area index (LAI) in 5 m resolution, sky view factor (SVF) in 1 m resolution, (c) total traffic emissions for 2018 (E_V , $\text{kg CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ a}^{-1}$) in 20 m resolution and (d) net biogenic flux for 2018 ($R_s + R_V - P_V$, $\text{kg CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ a}^{-1}$) in 20 m resolution. All maps are projected in UTM 32N (EPSG: 32632).

America and overall results are broadly comparable. The study by Christen et al. (2011) for a suburban area of Vancouver, Canada, demonstrated similar spatial patterns and orders of magnitude in annual total emissions for

all modelled components with the present study. The main differences between the two case studies is that the traffic in the main roads of the Vancouver case study exhibited higher emissions ($10.7 \text{ kg CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ a}^{-1}$)

Table 2
Annual flux totals for 2018 ($\text{kg CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ a}^{-1}$) and percent contribution per modelled flux component for the study area.

Building heating emissions	E_B	8.2	44.8 %	}	Buildings	11.0	60.1 %	
Commercial/industrial emissions	E_C	2.8	15.3 %					
Vehicle emissions	E_V	4.3	23.5 %	= >	Traffic	4.3	23.5 %	
Human respiration	R_H	3.3	18.0 %	= >	Human	3.3	18.0 %	
Soil respiration	R_S	1.0	5.5 %	}	Plants/soil	-0.3	-1.6 %	
Plant respiration	R_V	0.6	3.3 %					
Plant photosynthesis	P_V	-1.9	-10.4 %					
Total	F_C	18.3	100 %			18.3	100 %	

Table 3

Comparison between the model emissions for buildings and traffic within the study area with the official cantonal inventory statistics for CO₂ emissions. The inventory statistics for local building energy consumption, excluding the district heating and electricity, and the total consumption by vehicles are considered. The road lengths regard only the main, collecting and highway roads within the study area and the Canton, respectively. Values in parentheses are estimations that take into account highway traffic emissions.

	Units	Study Area (model)	Canton (inventory)
Land area	km ²	9.1	37.0
<i>Buildings</i>			
Emissions per area	kg CO ₂ m ⁻² a ⁻¹	11.0	6.1
Building volume per area	m ³ m ⁻²	4.7	2.3
Emissions per building volume	kg CO ₂ m ⁻³ a ⁻¹	2.3	2.7
<i>Traffic</i>			
Emissions per area	kg CO ₂ m ⁻² a ⁻¹	4.3 (7.3)	5.4
Road length	km	41.8	115.9
Emissions per road length	kg CO ₂ m ⁻¹ a ⁻¹	925.4 (1575.1)	1730.6

than in the Basel case study and that the human respiration in this residential area of Vancouver was lower (1.8 kg CO₂ m⁻² a⁻¹) than in the centre of Basel. The study by Järvi et al. (2019) using the SUEWS model showed nearly double traffic and human respiration emissions across Helsinki city centre compared to the present study, but the annual total (17.0 kg CO₂ m⁻² a⁻¹) is still similar to the Basel case study because of the minimal local building emissions in Helsinki, where space heating is covered by main central units. The diurnal profiles are similar between Basel and Helsinki case studies for the traffic emissions but not for the human respiration emissions (Järvi et al., 2019). For the latter, the SUEWS model exhibits very intense diurnal variability and extremely high total emissions in the city centre, stemming from the big differences between daytime and night-time population densities. As stated by Järvi et al. (2019), the daytime population datasets used in the model simulations may overestimate the number of employees present in certain areas due to the assumptions that all employees are present at the same time at their registered company headquarter area, something which is not realistic. The model presented here overcomes these drawbacks by making certain assumptions in employee spatial distribution (Section 2.6).

The Hestia product for Indianapolis, Indiana (Gurney et al., 2017, 2012) considers a wide area around the city, highlighting the increased traffic emissions concentrated in the city core and the main arterial roads around the city (6.5 kg CO₂ m⁻² a⁻¹), in contrast to the building emissions which concentrate mainly inside the city and are considerably lower in the city surroundings (2.1 kg CO₂ m⁻² a⁻¹ for the total area). Hestia uses similar diurnal and weekly emission profiles as the present model for commercial/industrial buildings (Gurney et al., 2012), following a workhour pattern with slight differences at the hours of peak emissions, where Hestia assumes an early morning peak and the present model a local noon peak. Hestia considers also a diurnal profile for space heating emissions in residential buildings (i.e. high during night and low during day), which is not accounted in the present model.

The biogenic flux model used in Christen et al. (2011) for Vancouver presented similar spatial patterns as the present study, where some areas behaved as sinks and others as sources in the total annual budget. The overall contribution of the biogenic components was low for Vancouver (-0.6 kg CO₂ m⁻² a⁻¹), similar to the case study of Basel. The SUEWS model estimates also that green areas in Helsinki city centre act mainly as a carbon sinks (Järvi et al., 2019), reaching sequestration potentials that vary between 0 and -2.7 kg CO₂ m⁻² a⁻¹. The biogenic flux modelling approaches presented by Velasco et al. (2016) for neighbourhoods of Mexico City and Singapore confirm that the sequestration potential of urban green areas is highly variable, acting as a sink in Mexico City (-1.3 kg CO₂ m⁻² a⁻¹) and as a source in Singapore (1.1 kg CO₂ m⁻²

a⁻¹). The latter is due to the warm and humid tropical climate which increases soil respiration (2.9 kg CO₂ m⁻² a⁻¹). The study of Hardiman et al. (2017) across the state of Massachusetts demonstrated also that urban biogenic components tend to present lower net carbon sequestration (e.g. -0.5 kg CO₂ m⁻² a⁻¹ in Boston) than the forested surroundings (-1.5 kg CO₂ m⁻² a⁻¹). On the other hand, several studies have highlighted that urban-specific growing conditions can enhance tree productivity (Briber et al., 2015; Zhao et al., 2016), suggesting that urban biogenic models cannot rely on parametrizations based on rural ecosystems (Hardiman et al., 2017).

Urban flux source/sink partitioning has also been attempted in literature by applying statistical methods on eddy covariance datasets (Crawford and Christen, 2015; Menzer and McFadden, 2017; Stagakis et al., 2019). An overview of the results of these studies is presented in Stagakis et al. (2019). There is high variability in the reported annual fluxes in these studies (6–37 kg CO₂ m⁻² a⁻¹), depending on the location of the eddy covariance tower. Suburban locations with high vegetation fractions (e.g. Menzer and McFadden, 2017; Ward et al., 2013) show much lower net annual fluxes compared to city centres mainly due to the lower anthropogenic emissions. The net annual biogenic fluxes reported in urban eddy covariance studies are similar, despite the location characteristics, and comparable to the modelled estimations of the present study (-0.8–0.3 kg CO₂ m⁻² a⁻¹).

4.5. Model evaluation

An extended study on the model application and evaluation is presented in Stagakis et al. (2022), considering 3 years (2018–2020) of hourly model simulations and concurrent F_C observations from two eddy covariance tower sites (BKLI, BAES) located within the study area. A summary of the model evaluation is presented in this paragraph. Hourly modelled F_C is compared to observed F_C by spatially aggregating the gridded modelled F_C according to normalized flux footprint functions using the Flux Footprint Prediction model (Kljun et al., 2015). Details on the eddy covariance tower characteristics, flux data analysis, post-processing and footprint modelling can be found in Stagakis et al. (2022). The flux data from the two towers are separated into two groups according to the prevailing wind directions (E, W) and evaluation statistics are extracted for different seasons and day types (Table 4). For each data group, the absolute differences between modelled and observed F_C are estimated by first averaging each dataset by hour of day and then extracting the diurnal means to avoid the bias of the random absent measurements (Stagakis et al., 2019).

This analysis provides an overview of the model performance for different periods and emission typologies. The modelled F_C agrees very well with the observed data for both seasons, day types and city areas, with mean differences ranging from -3.8 to 3.6 $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (Table 4). In most cases, the deviations between the means are proportionally higher during weekends. The hourly metrics, aggregated between seasons and day types, show mean absolute errors (MAE) ranging from 5.0 to 7.1 $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and root-mean-square errors (RMSE) ranging from 7.4 to 10.2 $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. These results are very promising and indicate that the model is able to capture very well both the spatial and temporal variability of the urban CO₂ fluxes. Previous studies which compared BU estimations to eddy covariance observations found similar ranges of error metrics and seasonal deviations of the means. The study of Christen et al. (2011) presented differences of monthly aggregated values between 0.6 and 4.1 $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (1.8–22.6 %), while the study of Wu et al. (2022) showed differences in seasonally aggregated means between -5.2–5.9 $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Hourly statistical metrics (RMSE) have been presented by Järvi et al. (2019) between 0.5 and 5.6 $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and by Wu et al. (2022) between 5.5 and 13.7 $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. It has to be noted that building heating emissions are negligible in the study of Järvi et al. (2019), which reduces the error sources in the comparison between the model and the observed data.

Table 4

Statistics of aggregated seasonal flux differences (Diff.) and hourly metrics (RMSE: root-mean-square error, MAE: mean absolute error) between eddy covariance measured F_C and hourly source area aggregated modelled F_C for each wind sector (W, E) of the two eddy covariance sites (BKLI, BAES). The statistics are given separately for winter (Oct – Apr) and summer (May – Sep) periods, weekdays (WD) and weekends (WE), and for the whole period. N states the number of data pairs.

	BKLI-E		BKLI-W		BAES-E		BAES-W	
	WD	WE	WD	WE	WD	WE	WD	WE
<i>Winter</i>								
Diff. ($\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$)	-1.7	-2.6	1.9	3.1	-3.8	-2.6	0.3	2.7
Diff. (%)	-8.5	-20.7	22.4	45.7	-23.1	-22.2	1.2	20.9
RMSE ($\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$)	10.9	8.9	7.9	7.1	9.5	8.2	10.6	9.1
MAE ($\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$)	7.7	6.0	5.5	5.1	6.5	5.7	8.2	7.0
N	4709	1815	2735	1146	4568	1905	3023	1166
<i>Summer</i>								
Diff. ($\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$)	-1.4	-1.0	0.3	1.6	1.8	2.8	0.5	3.6
Diff. (%)	-8.3	-12.0	3.6	32.7	18.9	62.0	2.4	37.0
RMSE ($\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$)	10.5	8.4	7.9	5.6	6.5	6.3	8.6	7.4
MAE ($\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$)	7.3	5.7	4.9	3.9	4.5	4.3	6.4	6.1
N	3187	1147	2650	1162	2037	750	2877	1118
<i>All</i>								
Diff. ($\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$)	-2.2		1.5		-2.1		1.0	
Diff. (%)	-12.8		20.2		-15.6		5.2	
RMSE ($\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$)	10.2		7.4		8.4		9.3	
MAE ($\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$)	7.1		5.0		5.7		7.1	
N	10,860		7693		9261		8184	

4.6. Model restrictions

Emissions from a city can be much more complex than represented in this study. The model is designed for city-scale applicability and focussed on the local surface CO_2 fluxes, therefore it presents several restrictions. The building emission part of the model relies on general temporal and spatial proxies (i.e. single heating energy consumption function, building volume/type) and therefore cannot describe the variability induced by the various building typologies and energy use efficiencies. The characterisation of the emissions by commercial/industrial activities is further simplified and does not consider the types of activities which would define the emission rates. Therefore, the model outputs are not ideal for extracting building-level planning decisions, such as energy renovation strategies. Additionally, the model does not take into account industrial power plant emissions, which would be essential for deriving the total emissions of extended areas, such as cantons or municipalities and be used for direct comparison and evaluation of the current inventories. The vehicle emission model is based on the number and types of vehicles per road segment and aggregated emission factors but does not take into account spatially resolved estimations of driving mode, vehicle speed, congestion, idling or environmental effects. It is therefore expected that the model can provide a general spatiotemporal overview of the emissions per road type but not explicitly locate and characterize driving condition and road network attributes in increased detail (e.g. intersection or bottleneck effects). Moreover, the rising number of electric vehicles in the fleet during the recent years is a parameter that should be accounted in the aggregated emission factor estimation.

In contrast to restrictions on the detail of building and vehicle emissions, the model incorporates human respiration and the biogenic components in greater detail than other studies. For example, it is the first time to our knowledge that a photosynthesis model takes into account the complex urban morphology in a 3D multilayer radiation interception algorithm. Nevertheless, several enhancements are possible to improve the human and biogenic emissions in the model, such as using more detailed datasets for population density dynamics (e.g. mobile phone data) and accounting for more urban-specific growing conditions in the biogenic models (e.g. N fertilization, temperature spatial variability, elevated CO_2). Specifically, the biogenic flux model applied in this study assumes similar photosynthetic behaviour among different vegetation types and species across the study area, simplifying the extreme diversity which is expected in the urban environment. Variability in photosynthetic capacities is more pronounced between different vegetation types, with grasses being potentially more

productive than trees during the growing season (Larcher, 2003). Additionally, there are other potential sources of error in the biogenic model, such as the satellite-based LAI estimation and the approximation of θ spatial variability which is based only on three station measurements and does not account for irrigation in private gardens.

A sensitivity analysis has been performed to evaluate the expected biases in the biogenic model estimations according to the uncertainties of these three key inputs (LAI, A_{max} , θ). The results are provided in the Supplementary material. The sensitivity analysis indicates that when considering increased photosynthetic capacity during the whole year for grasses then the total P_V across the study area can increase by $0.4 \text{ kg CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ a}^{-1}$, which translates to 2.0 % of the net F_C . Accordingly, LAI and θ uncertainties provided model biases of similar orders of magnitude (Table S.6). Considering the small contribution of the biogenic flux variabilities on the net urban F_C , a simplified model version of the biogenic fluxes can be sufficient for a general urban CO_2 flux study. Higher precision in urban biogenic flux modelling would be relevant if the investigation is specifically focussed on the effects that urban vegetation has on the urban CO_2 fluxes at particular time periods (e.g. summer daytime hours) or on scenarios for urban vegetation productivity optimisation.

Uncertainty quantification for the model outputs would be important, especially because the model is intended to be combined with atmospheric observations in data assimilation schemes (Stagakis et al., 2022). As previously stated by several other studies (e.g. Gately et al., 2017; Järvi et al., 2019; Lauvaux et al., 2016), uncertainty quantification in BU emission models are difficult to analytically estimate due to the lack of uncertainty information for key model input data (e.g. traffic counts, census data, emission factors) and because some model approximations for the spatial variability of the emissions are empirical, generic or simplistic, which makes it difficult to assign uncertainties spatially. For the biogenic flux models, which retain an analytical representation of the physiological processes, input variances can be obtained from literature and model uncertainties can be quantified using probabilistic approaches (e.g. Santaren et al., 2007; Trotsiuk et al., 2020). Due to the relatively small effect of the biogenic components to the total balance in the study area, such detailed analysis is not performed in the present study. Uncertainty and sensitivity analyses on the biogenic models is planned to be part of future model applications in more extended study areas, covering significant green area fractions. In the present application, uncertainty quantification is performed in the second part of this study, where the BU model estimations are constrained by eddy covariance observations within a probabilistic inversion framework (Stagakis et al., 2022).

5. Conclusions

A new high-resolution bottom-up (BU) model for local urban CO₂ fluxes is presented. The model provides independent hourly 20 m resolution estimates of each component contributing to the local surface CO₂ flux: i) building emissions, ii) traffic emissions, iii) human respiration, iv) soil respiration, v) plant respiration and vi) plant photosynthetic uptake, based primarily on geospatial, meteorological, census and traffic count datasets. The model is applied on the city centre of Basel for the year 2018. It is demonstrated that the model captures the highly dynamic spatio-temporal variability of the urban CO₂ fluxes, describing the seasonality of the building emissions according to temperature, the effects of building density and building types, the differences in the traffic emissions at different road types, as well as the intense variability of the biogenic fluxes according to local meteorology, green area management and urban morphology. It is estimated that building emissions contribute 60.1 %, traffic 23.5 %, human respiration 18 % and the biogenic components – 1.6 % to the total annual CO₂ balance of the study area. The annual model estimates for building and traffic emissions are compared to the official inventory statistics of the Basel Canton and differences of 14.8 % and 9 % are found, respectively, with the model showing lower emissions than the inventory for both components. These differences are mainly attributed to the restricted geographical coverage of the model area which does not take fully into account the strong emissions by the commercial/industrial sector and the highways that cross the Cantonal area.

The model is designed to provide prior surface CO₂ flux estimates for direct comparison with in-situ atmospheric observations and development of local scale atmospheric inversion methodologies. The second part of this study (Stagakis et al., 2022) describes the comparison between the BU model estimates and hourly CO₂ flux measured by two eddy covariance systems in the study area, and the development of a probabilistic inversion methodology to constrain the BU estimates with the eddy covariance observations and to provide optimised hourly fluxes and associated uncertainties.

Funding

This research has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie, grant agreement No 836443.

Appendix A. Canopy radiation interception algorithm

The canopy radiation interception algorithm divides the study area into voxels of 5 × 5 × 5 m, categorized as air, terrain, building or vegetation according to DSM and land cover products. Tree maximum and minimum height, derived by the LiDAR point cloud, is used to define tree crown voxels. Vegetation voxels are attributed to a LAI value assuming that total LAI, derived by S2, is distributed homogeneously across the horizontal levels occupied by vegetation. Sky view factor (SVF) is estimated for each voxel using the SVF plugin of the Urban Multi-scale Environmental Predictor (UMEP) software tool (Lindberg et al., 2018). Total and directional (from the 4 cardinal points) SVF is estimated for each voxel (Lindberg and Grimmond, 2011) taking into account the full DSM (Ψ_f) and the DSM without trees (Ψ_b). SVF at voxels classified as buildings or vegetation is masked.

The fractions of sunlit and shaded LAI in each voxel (k) are modelled following Campbell and Norman (1998) as:

$$LAI_{sun,k} = \frac{1}{k_b} \cdot e^{-k_b \cdot LAI_{0,k}} \cdot (1 - e^{-k_b \cdot LAI_k}) \cdot Sh_k \quad (A.1)$$

$$k_b = \frac{1}{2 \cdot \sin \eta} \quad (A.2)$$

$$LAI_{shade,k} = LAI_k - LAI_{sun,k} \quad (A.3)$$

$LAI_{0,k}$ is the sum of LAI intersected by the direct radiation beam before reaching the LAI voxel in position k . For the estimation of $LAI_{0,k}$, the ray tracing algorithm of Amanatides and Woo (1987) is applied on the LAI 3d grid to detect the voxels intersected by the beam according to sun position. The code of Mena-Chalco (2010) is modified to estimate ray origin and direction for each grid voxel according to sun elevation (η) and azimuth angles and the input 3d grid dimensions. Sh_k is a Boolean value which provides information on the presence (0) or absence (1) of shadow by buildings or terrain at voxel k , estimated by the ray tracing algorithm. k_b is the radiation extinction coefficient for direct radiation adopting spherical leaf angle distribution (Campbell, 1986; Campbell and Norman, 1998).

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Stavros Stagakis: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Software, Investigation, Methodology, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Christian Feigenwinter:** Data curation, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Roland Vogt:** Resources, Data curation, Supervision, Project administration, Writing – review & editing. **Markus Kalberer:** Resources, Project administration, Writing – review & editing.

Data availability

All datasets produced for the present study are available in Zenodo repository under Creative Commons Licence CC-BY-4.0:

- Land Cover (doi:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6511967>)
- Digital Surface Models (doi:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7189252>)
- Population density (doi:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7189315>)
- Leaf Area Index (doi:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7189509>)
- In-situ meteorological dataset (doi:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7189850>)
- CO₂ flux maps (doi:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7190303>)

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

Basel city authorities (Tiefbauamt Basel-Stadt) are acknowledged for providing the LiDAR point cloud dataset. The Authors would also like to thank Assoc. Prof. Andrea Pitacco (University of Padova) and Assoc. Prof. Aris Kyriarissis (University of Thessaly) for their feedback on the biogenic flux model development. Dr. Robert Spirig and Günter Bing are acknowledged for their support in coding, database handling and other technical issues. Three anonymous Reviewers are acknowledged for their valuable insights and suggestions that helped to improve the manuscript.

The PAR ($\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) reaching leaf surface at each voxel (k) is modelled separately for its different components as:

$$PAR_{dir,sun} = (1 - \rho_l) \cdot PAR_{dir} \cdot \sin\eta \cdot k_b \quad (\text{A.4})$$

$$PAR_{dif,k} = (1 - \rho_l) \cdot PAR_{dif} \cdot \left(\Psi_f \cdot \tau_{(k_d),k\downarrow} + \Psi_{f_{N,k}} \cdot \tau_{(k_d),k\rightarrow} + \Psi_{f_{E,k}} \cdot \tau_{(k_d),k\rightarrow} + \Psi_{f_{S,k}} \cdot \tau_{(k_d),k\rightarrow} + \Psi_{f_{W,k}} \cdot \tau_{(k_d),k\rightarrow} \right) \quad (\text{A.5})$$

$$PAR_{sc,k} = (1 - \rho_l) \cdot PAR_{dir} \cdot \sin\eta \cdot (\tau_{(k_b),k\downarrow} - e^{-k_b \cdot LAI_{0,k}}) \cdot Sh_k \quad (\text{A.6})$$

$$PAR_{ref,k} = (1 - \rho_l) \cdot PAR_{glob} \cdot \rho_b \cdot \sin\eta \cdot \left[(1 - \Psi b_k) \cdot \tau_{(k_d),k\downarrow} + (0.5 - \Psi b_{N,k}) \cdot \tau_{(k_d),k\rightarrow} + (0.5 - \Psi b_{E,k}) \cdot \tau_{(k_d),k\rightarrow} + (0.5 - \Psi b_{S,k}) \cdot \tau_{(k_d),k\rightarrow} + (0.5 - \Psi b_{W,k}) \cdot \tau_{(k_d),k\rightarrow} \right] \quad (\text{A.7})$$

$$\tau_{(x),k} = e^{-\sqrt{1 - \rho_l} \cdot x \cdot LAI_{0,k}} \quad (\text{A.8})$$

$PAR_{dir,sun}$ is the direct PAR on sunlit leaves, $PAR_{dif,k}$ is the diffuse PAR on voxel k , $PAR_{sc,k}$ is the down-scattered radiation due to multiple scattering inside the tree crowns (Campbell and Norman, 1998), and $PAR_{ref,k}$ is the reflected radiation by urban surroundings following the simplified approximation of Lindberg (2007). ρ_l and ρ_b are constants for the leaf and built material reflectance of PAR (Table S.5). PAR_{dir} , PAR_{dif} and PAR_{glob} are the measured direct, diffuse and global PAR respectively. SVF (Ψ_f and Ψ_b) subscripts (N, E, S, W) correspond to directional estimates for the respective part of hemisphere. $\tau_{(x),k}$ represents the fraction of PAR transmitted through tree canopy towards each direction (the respective arrow indicates downwards or directional) considering the light scattering effects inside the canopy (Campbell and Norman, 1998). $LAI_{0,k}$ is the sum of LAI towards the respective direction before reaching voxel k until the edge of the tree crown. Overlapping tree crowns in the same horizontal layer are treated as a unique crown. Eq. (A.8) works well for both direct and diffuse radiation (Campbell and Norman, 1998) using the respective extinction coefficient (x). For diffuse radiation, k_d is assumed constant for spherical leaf angle distributions (Campbell and Norman, 1998; De Pury and Farquhar, 1997; Spitters, 1986) at 0.7.

In total, the PAR on sunlit and the shaded LAI for the whole study area 3d grid are calculated as:

$$PAR_{sun} = PAR_{dir,sun} + PAR_{dif} + PAR_{sc} + PAR_{ref} \quad (\text{A.9})$$

$$PAR_{shade} = PAR_{dif} + PAR_{sc} + PAR_{ref} \quad (\text{A.10})$$

Appendix B. Environmental controls on leaf photosynthesis and respiration

Leaf photosynthesis and respiration dependence on PAR, T_{air} , VPD and θ are modelled as:

$$A_{net} = A_{max} \cdot \left(1 - e^{-\frac{a \cdot PAR}{A_{max}}} \right) - 0.5 \cdot R_l \quad (\text{B.1})$$

$$f(T_{air}) = \exp \left[-\frac{(T_{air} - T_{opt})^2}{2 \cdot W^2} \right] \quad (\text{B.2})$$

$$R_l = R_{l,ref} \cdot Q_{10}^{\frac{T_{air} - T_{ref,l}}{10}} \quad (\text{B.3})$$

$$c_i = c_s - \frac{A_{net} \cdot f(T_{air})}{\left(1 - \frac{(\theta_{ref} - \theta)^{b_1}}{(\theta_{ref} - \theta_s)^{b_1}} \right) \cdot \left(g_o + a_1 \cdot \frac{A_{net} \cdot f(T_{air})}{(1 + \frac{VPD}{D_o}) \cdot (c_i - \Gamma)} \right)} \quad (\text{B.4})$$

$$f(VPD\theta) = \frac{\min \left[\frac{V_{max} \cdot (c_i - \Gamma)}{c_i + K_c \cdot (1 + \frac{\theta_i}{K_\theta})} \cdot \frac{J \cdot (c_i - \Gamma)}{4 \cdot (c_i + 2 \cdot \Gamma)} \right]}{\min \left[\frac{V_{max} \cdot (c_{i,ref} - \Gamma)}{c_{i,ref} + K_c \cdot (1 + \frac{\theta_i}{K_\theta})} \cdot \frac{J \cdot (c_{i,ref} - \Gamma)}{4 \cdot (c_{i,ref} + 2 \cdot \Gamma)} \right]} \quad (\text{B.5})$$

Eq. (B.1) models net leaf photosynthesis (A_{net}) using a simplified version of the nonrectangular hyperbola (Thornley and Johnson, 1990) which considers A_{max} (maximum gross photosynthetic rate) and a (quantum yield for CO_2 assimilation). A_{max} and a are kept constant across the study area (Table S.5). Eq. (B.2) follows the empirical peaked function by June et al. (2004), where T_{opt} is the optimum T_{air} for photosynthesis and W is width of the curve at $f(T_{air}) = 0.5$. Eq. (B.3) is an exponential fixed- Q_{10} equation for estimating leaf respiration dependence on temperature (Heskel et al., 2016). Our approach assumes a 50 % inhibition of dark respiration during day for all species (e.g. Atkin et al., 2000; Brooks and Farquhar, 1985; Peisker and Apel, 2001; Villar et al., 1995).

Atmospheric humidity and soil moisture deficits are known to have direct effects on stomatal conductance (g_s) rather than photosynthetic capacity (Lösch and Tenhunen, 1981; Ludlow, 1980), nevertheless, by inducing stomata closure, the intercellular CO_2 concentration (c_i) is reduced, limiting leaf gross photosynthetic rate (Egea et al., 2011; Keenan et al., 2010; Zhou et al., 2013). Eq. (B.4) gives the expected value of c_i according to g_s , based on Leuning (1995), adding an empirical factor for simulating θ constrains. c_s is the CO_2 compensation point at the leaf surface (assumed constant), g_o is the residual stomatal conductance (i.e. g_s when $A_{net} = 0$, $\text{PAR} = 0$), Γ is the CO_2 compensation point (i.e. c_i when $A_{net} = 0$), θ_{ref} and θ_g are the reference soil moisture (at water saturation) and the lowest limit to g_s , respectively, while D_o , a_1 and b_1 are empirical coefficients (Table S.5). Eq. (B.4) is used to estimate “actual” c_i (based on measured VPD, θ) and reference $c_{i,ref}$ (VPD = 0, $\theta = \theta_{ref}$). $f(VPD, \theta)$ is modelled by simulating the respective changes in photosynthesis according to the c_i gradient (Eq. (B.5)) based on the photosynthesis model of Farquhar et al. (1980) and by keeping all parameters of the model constant except c_i .

Electron transport rate (J) in Eq. (B.5) follows a non-rectangular hyperbolic function based on PAR similar to Eq. (B.1). The constant values used in Eq. (B.5) are given in Table S.5.

The parametrization of Eqs. (B.1)–(B.5), as well as Eq. (16) for soil respiration, is based on literature values (Table S.5), combined to field measurements performed on the 5 most abundant tree species in the study site and several soil locations during 2020 (data still unpublished).

Appendix C. Supplementary material

Supplementary material to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.160216>.

References

- Amanatides, J., Woo, A., 1987. A fast voxel traversal algorithm for ray tracing. *Eurographics* 87, 3–10.
- Amtliche Vermessung Basel-Stadt, 2021]. Bau- und Verkehrsdepartement, Grundbuch- und Vermessungsamt Amtliche Vermessung. https://www.geocat.ch/geonetwork/srv/ger/md.viewer#/full_view/769225cf-1b31-46c9-ac74-6f41aaf832f6.
- Atkin, O.K., Evans, J.R., Ball, M.C., Lambers, H., Pons, T.L., 2000. Leaf respiration of snow gum in the light and dark. Interactions between temperature and irradiance. *Plant Physiol.* 122, 915–923. <https://doi.org/10.1104/pp.122.3.915>.
- Bellucco, V., Marras, S., Grimmond, C.S.B., Järvi, L., Sirca, C., Spano, D., 2017. Modelling the biogenic CO₂ exchange in urban and non-urban ecosystems through the assessment of light-response curve parameters. *Agric. For. Meteorol.* 236, 113–122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2016.12.011>.
- Beschäftigte und Arbeitsstätten, 2021]. Beschäftigte und Arbeitsstätten nach block. <https://www.basleratlas.ch/#c=home>.
- Briber, B.M., Hutryra, L.R., Reinmann, A.B., Raciti, S.M., Dearborn, V.K., Holden, C.E., Dunn, A.L., 2015. Tree productivity enhanced with conversion from forest to urban land covers. *PLoS One* 10. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0136237>.
- Brooks, A., Farquhar, G.D., 1985. Effect of temperature on the CO₂/O₂ specificity of ribulose-1,5-bisphosphate carboxylase/oxygenase and the rate of respiration in the light - estimates from gas-exchange measurements on spinach. *Planta* 165, 397–406. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00392238>.
- Buck, A.L., 1981. New equations for computing vapour pressure and enhancement factor. *J. Appl. Meteorol.* 20. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0450\(1981\)020<1527:nefcvp>2.0.co;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0450(1981)020<1527:nefcvp>2.0.co;2).
- C-40, 2022. C-40 Cities Leadership Group. <https://www.c40.org/> (accessed 24 June 2022).
- Campbell, G.S., 1986. Extinction coefficients for radiation in plant canopies calculated using an ellipsoidal inclination angle distribution. *Agric. For. Meteorol.* 36, 317–321. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1923\(86\)90010-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1923(86)90010-9).
- Campbell, G.S., Norman, J.M., 1998. The light environment of plant canopies. An Introduction to Environmental Biophysics https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4612-1626-1_15.
- Chen, G., Shan, Y., Hu, Y., Tong, K., Wiedmann, T., Ramaswami, A., Guan, D., Shi, L., Wang, Y., 2019. Review on city-level carbon accounting. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 53. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.8b07071>.
- Christen, A., Coops, N.C., Crawford, B.R., Kellett, R., Liss, K.N., Olchovski, I., Tooke, T.R., Van Der Laan, M., Voogt, J.A., 2011. Validation of modeled carbon-dioxide emissions from an urban neighborhood with direct eddy-covariance measurements. *Atmos. Environ.* 45, 6057–6069. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2011.07.040>.
- Chrysoulakis, N., Lopes, M., San José, R., Grimmond, C.S.B., Jones, M.B., Magliulo, V., Klostermann, J.E.M., Synnefa, A., Mitraka, Z., Castro, E.A., González, A., Vogt, R., Vesala, T., Spano, D., Pigeon, G., Freer-Smith, P., Staszewski, T., Hodges, N., Mills, G., Cartalis, C., 2013. Sustainable urban metabolism as a link between bio-physical sciences and urban planning: the BRIDGE project. *Landsc. Urban Plan.* 112, 100–117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2012.12.005>.
- CO2 Blue Report, 2015. Towards a European Operational Observing System to Monitor Fossil CO₂ emissions: Final Report from the expert group, European Commission, 2015. https://www.copernicus.eu/sites/default/files/2019-09/CO2_Blue_report_2015.pdf (accessed 24 June 2022).
- Crawford, B., Christen, A., 2015. Spatial source attribution of measured urban eddy covariance CO₂ fluxes. *Theor. Appl. Climatol.* 119, 733–755. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00704-014-1124-0>.
- De Pury, D.G.G., Farquhar, G.D., 1997. Simple scaling of photosynthesis from leaves to canopies without the errors of big-leaf models. *Plant Cell Environ.* 20. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3040.1997.00094.x>.
- Decina, S.M., Hutryra, L.R., Gately, C.K., Getson, J.M., Reinmann, A.B., Short Gianotti, A.G., Templer, P.H., 2016. Soil respiration contributes substantially to urban carbon fluxes in the greater Boston area. *Environ. Pollut.* 212, 433–439. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2016.01.012>.
- D-Stadtmodell, 2021. Grundbuch- und Vermessungsamt Amtliche Vermessung. https://www.geocat.ch/geonetwork/srv/ger/md.viewer#/full_view/a7fcab8f-8b17-4559-a77b-9df91bef5e1a.
- EC, 2022. European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, EU Missions: 100 Climate-neutral and Smart Cities. <https://doi.org/10.2777/191876> (accessed 24 June 2022).
- Egea, G., Verhoef, A., Vidale, P.L., 2011. Towards an improved and more flexible representation of water stress in coupled photosynthesis-stomatal conductance models. *Agric. For. Meteorol.* 151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2011.05.019>.
- Energiestatistik Basel-Stadt, 2020. Herausgeber Statistisches Amt des Kantons Basel-Stadt, Mai 2020. <https://www.statistik.bs.ch/analysen-berichte/raum-umwelt/energiestatistik.html> (accessed 24 June 2022).
- Farquhar, G.D., von Caemmerer, S., Berry, J.A., 1980. A biochemical model of photosynthetic CO₂ assimilation in leaves of C₃ species. *Planta* 149, 78–90. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00386231>.
- Friedlingstein, P., O'Sullivan, M., Jones, M.W., Andrew, R.M., Hauck, J., Olsen, A., Peters, G.P., Peters, W., Pongratz, J., Sitch, S., Le Quééré, C., Canadell, J.G., Ciais, P., Jackson, R.B., Alin, S., Aragão, L.E.O.C., Arneeth, A., Arora, V., Bates, N.R., Becker, M., Benoit-Cattin, A., Bittig, H.C., Bopp, L., Bultan, S., Chandra, N., Chevallier, F., Chini, L.P., Evans, W., Florentie, L., Forster, P.M., Gasser, T., Gehlen, M., Gilfillan, D., Gkritzalis, T., Gregor, L., Gruber, N., Harris, I., Hartung, K., Haverd, V., Houghton, R.A., Ilyina, T., Jain, A.K., Joetzjer, E., Kadono, K., Kato, E., Kitidis, V., Korsbakken, J.I., Landschützer, P., Lefèvre, N., Lenton, A., Lienert, S., Liu, Z., Lombardozi, D., Marland, G., Metzl, N., Munro, D.R., Nabel, J.E.M.S., Nakaoka, S.I., Niwa, Y., O'Brien, K., Ono, T., Palmer, P.I., Pierrot, D., Poulter, B., Resplandy, L., Robertson, E., Rödenbeck, C., Schwingler, J., Séférian, R., Skjelvan, I., Smith, A.J.P., Sutton, A.J., Tanhua, T., Tans, P.P., Tian, H., Tilbrook, B., Van Der Werf, G., Vuichard, N., Walker, A.P., Wanninkhof, R., Watson, A.J., Willis, D., Wiltshire, A.J., Yuan, W., Yue, X., Zaehele, S., 2020. Global carbon budget 2020. *Earth Syst. Sci. Data* 12. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-12-3269-2020>.
- Gately, C.K., Hutryra, L.R., Peterson, S., Sue Wing, I., 2017. Urban emissions hotspots: quantifying vehicle congestion and air pollution using mobile phone GPS data. *Environ. Pollut.* 229, 496–504. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2017.05.091>.
- GCofM CRF, 2018. Global Covenant of Mayors: Common Reporting Framework, Version 6.1, September 2018. https://www.globalcovenantofmayors.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/04/FINAL_Data-TWG_Reporting-Framework_website_FINAL-13-Sept-2018_for-translation.pdf (accessed 24 June 2022).
- Gebäudeadressen und -informationen, 2022]. Bau- und Verkehrsdepartement, Grundbuch- und Vermessungsamt Fachstelle für Geoinformation. https://www.geocat.ch/geonetwork/srv/ger/md.viewer#/full_view/52a35a63-b873-48ce-800b-b5624f1da3e7.
- GHG Protocol, 2021. Global Protocol for Community-Scale Greenhouse Gas Inventories: An Accounting and Reporting Standard for Cities, Version 1.1. https://ghgprotocol.org/sites/default/files/standards/GPC_Full_MASTER_RW_v7.pdf (accessed 24 June 2022).
- Global Covenant of Mayors, 2022. Global Covenant of Mayors for Climate & Energy. <https://www.globalcovenantofmayors.org/> accessed 24 June 2022.
- GMES/Copernicus land monitoring services, 2018]. European Urban Atlas. European Environment Agency (EEA). <https://land.copernicus.eu/local/urban-atlas/urban-atlas-2018>.
- Grenzgänger nach Geschlecht und Wohnsitzstaat, 2022. Statistisches Amt Basel-Stadt. <https://www.statistik.bs.ch/haeufig-gefragt/arbeiten/grenzgaenger.html> (accessed 24 June 2022).
- Guevara, M., Martínez, F., Arévalo, G., Gassó, S., Baldasano, J.M., 2013. An improved system for modelling Spanish emissions: HERMESv2.0. *Atmos. Environ.* 81, 209–221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2013.08.053>.
- Guevara, M., Tena, C., Porquet, M., Jorba, O., Pérez García-Pando, C., 2020. HERMESv3, a stand-alone multi-scale atmospheric emission modelling framework-part 2: the bottom-up module. *Geosci. Model Dev.* 13, 873–903. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-13-873-2020>.
- Gurney, K.R., Mendoza, D.L., Zhou, Y., Fischer, M.L., Miller, C.C., Geethakumar, S., Du Can, S.D.L.R., 2009. High resolution fossil fuel combustion CO₂ emission fluxes for the United States. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 43. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es900806c>.
- Gurney, K.R., Razlivanov, I., Song, Y., Zhou, Y., Benes, B., Abdul-Massih, M., 2012. Quantification of fossil fuel CO₂ emissions on the building/street scale for a large U.S. city. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 46. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es3011282>.
- Gurney, K.R., Liang, J., Patarasuk, R., O'Keefe, D., Huang, J., Hutchins, M., Lauvaux, T., Turnbull, J.C., Shepson, P.B., 2017. Reconciling the differences between a bottom-up and inverse-estimated FFCO₂ emissions estimate in a large US urban area. *Elementa* 5. <https://doi.org/10.1525/elementa.137>.
- Gurney, K.R., Liang, J., Patarasuk, R., Song, Y., Huang, J., Roest, G., 2020. The Vulcan version 3.0 high-resolution fossil fuel CO₂ emissions for the United States. *J. Geophys. Res.* Atmos. 125. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020JD032974>.
- Gurney, K.R., Liang, J., Roest, G., Song, Y., Mueller, K., Lauvaux, T., 2021. Under-reporting of greenhouse gas emissions in U.S. cities. *Nat. Commun.* 12. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-20871-0>.
- Hagolle, O., Huc, M., Descardins, C., Auer, S., Richter, R., 2017. MAJA Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1209633>.
- Hardiman, B.S., Wang, J.A., Hutryra, L.R., Gately, C.K., Getson, J.M., Friedl, M.A., 2017. Accounting for urban biogenic fluxes in regional carbon budgets. *Sci. Total Environ.* 592, 366–372. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.03.028>.
- HBEFA 4.1, 2021. Development Report. https://www.hbefa.net/e/documents/HBEFA41_Development_Report.pdf (accessed 24 June 2022).
- Heskel, M.A., O'Sullivan, O.S., Reich, P.B., Tjoelker, M.G., Weerasinghe, L.K., Penillard, A., Egerton, J.J.G., Creek, D., Bloomfield, K.J., Xiang, J., Sinca, F., Stangl, Z.R., Martinez-De La Torre, A., Griffin, K.L., Huntingford, C., Hurry, V., Meir, P., Turnbull, M.H., Atkin, O.K., 2016. Convergence in the temperature response of leaf respiration across biomes and plant functional types. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 113. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1520282113>.

- ICLEI, 2022. International Council for Local Environmental Initiative. <https://iclei.org/> (accessed 24 June 2022).
- IPCC, 2006. (prepared by the National Greenhouse Gas Inventory Programme) In: Eggleston, S., Buendia, L., Miwa, K., Ngara, T., Tanabe, K. (Eds.), IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories, published by the Institute for Global Environmental Strategies, Hayama, Japan, IPCC-TSU NGGIP, IGES, Hayama, Japan (accessed 24 June 2022) <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/2006-ipcc-guidelines-for-national-greenhouse-gas-inventories/>.
- IPCC, 2022. Climate Change 2022: Mitigation of Climate Change. Summary for policymakers. Contribution of Working Group III to the 6th Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. https://report.ipcc.ch/ar6wg3/pdf/IPCC_AR6_WGIII_SummaryForPolicymakers.pdf (accessed 24 June 2022).
- Janssens-Maenhout, G., Crippa, M., Guizzardi, D., Muntean, M., Schaaf, E., Dentener, F., Bergamaschi, P., Pagliari, V., Olivier, J.G.J., Peters, J.A.H.W., Van Aardenne, J.A., Monni, S., Doering, U., Roxana Petrescu, A.M., Solazzo, E., Oreggioni, G.D., 2019. EDGAR v4.3.2 Global Atlas of the three major greenhouse gas emissions for the period 1970–2012. *Earth Syst. Sci. Data* 11. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-11-959-2019>.
- Järvi, L., Grimmond, C.S.B., Christen, A., 2011. The surface urban energy and water balance scheme (SUEWS): evaluation in Los Angeles and Vancouver. *J. Hydrol.* 411, 219–237. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2011.10.001>.
- Järvi, L., Havu, M., Ward, H.C., Bellucco, V., McFadden, J.P., Toivonen, T., Heikinheimo, V., Kolari, P., Riikonen, A., Grimmond, C.S.B., 2019. Spatial modeling of local-scale biogenic and anthropogenic carbon dioxide emissions in Helsinki. *J. Geophys. Res. Atmos.* 124, 8363–8384. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018JD029576>.
- June, T., Evans, J.R., Farquhar, G.D., 2004. A simple new equation for the reversible temperature dependence of photosynthetic electron transport: a study on soybean leaf. *Funct. Plant Biol.* 31, 275–283. <https://doi.org/10.1071/FP03250>.
- Kantonaler Richtplan Teilrichtplan Energie, 2020. Departement für Wirtschaft, Soziales und Umwelt des Kantons Basel-Stadt, Amt für Umwelt und Energie, März. <https://www.aue.bs.ch/energie/gebaeude-energie/energierichtplan.html> (accessed 24 June 2022).
- Keenan, T., Sabate, S., Gracia, C., 2010. The importance of mesophyll conductance in regulating forest ecosystem productivity during drought periods. *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 16, 1019–1034. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2009.02017.x>.
- Kljun, N., Calanca, P., Rotach, M.W., Schmid, H.P., 2015. A simple two-dimensional parameterisation for Flux Footprint Prediction (FFP). *Geosci. Model Dev.* 8, 3695–3713. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-8-3695-2015>.
- Larcher, W., 2003. *Physiological Plant Ecology: Ecophysiology and Stress Physiology of Functional Groups*. 4th ed. Springer, Berlin.
- Lauvaux, T., Miles, N.L., Deng, A., Richardson, S.J., Cambaliza, M.O., Davis, K.J., Gaudet, B., Gurney, K.R., Huang, J., O'Keefe, D., Song, Y., Karion, A., Oda, T., Patarasuk, R., Razlivanov, I., Sarmiento, D., Shepson, P., Sweeney, C., Turnbull, J., Wu, K., 2016. High-resolution atmospheric inversion of urban CO₂ emissions during the dormant season of the Indianapolis flux experiment (INFLUX). *J. Geophys. Res.* 121, 5213–5236. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2015JD024473>.
- Leuning, R., 1995. A critical appraisal of a combined stomatal-photosynthesis model for C₃ plants. *Plant Cell Environ.* 18, 339–355. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3040.1995.tb00370.x>.
- Lietzke, B., Vogt, R., Feigenwinter, C., Parlow, E., 2015. On the controlling factors for the variability of carbon dioxide flux in a heterogeneous urban environment. *Int. J. Climatol.* 35, 3921–3941. <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.4255>.
- Lindberg, F., 2007. Modelling the urban climate using a local governmental geo-database. *Meteorol. Appl.* 14, 263–273. <https://doi.org/10.1002/met.29>.
- Lindberg, F., Grimmond, C.S.B., 2011. The influence of vegetation and building morphology on shadow patterns and mean radiant temperatures in urban areas: Model development and evaluation. *Theor. Appl. Climatol.* 105, 311–323. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00704-010-0382-8>.
- Lindberg, F., Grimmond, C.S.B., Gabey, A., Huang, B., Kent, C.W., Sun, T., Theeuwes, N.E., Järvi, L., Ward, H.C., Capel-Timmis, I., Chang, Y., Jonsson, P., Krave, N., Liu, D., Meyer, D., Olofson, K.F.G., Tan, J., Wästberg, D., Xue, L., Zhang, Z., 2018. Urban Multi-scale Environmental Predictor (UMEP): An integrated tool for city-based climate services. *Environ. Model. Softw.* 99, 70–87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2017.09.020>.
- Liss, K., Crawford, B., Christen, A., Siemens, C., Jassal, R., 2009. Ecosystem respiration of suburban lawns and its response to varying management and irrigation regimes. AMS Eighth Conference on the Urban Environment, Phoenix, AZ, USA.
- Lloyd, J., Taylor, J.A., 1994. On the temperature dependence of soil respiration. *Funct. Ecol.* 8, 315–323. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2389824>.
- Löscher, R., Tenhunen, J.D., 1981. Stomatal responses to humidity—phenomenon and mechanism. *Stomatal Physiol.* 137–161.
- Ludlow, M.M., 1980. Adaptive significance of stomatal responses to water stress. In: Turner, N.C., Kramer, P.J. (Eds.), *Adaptation of Plants to Water and High Temperature Stress*. John Wiley and Sons, New York, pp. 123–137.
- MacKerron, D.K.L., 2005. Agrometeorology: principles and application of climate studies in agriculture. In: Mavi, H.S., Tupper, G.J. (Eds.), *Experimental Agriculture*. Haworth Press, Binghamton, NY, p. 364 <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0014479704212613>.
- MATLAB griddata, 2022. Interpolate 2-D or 3-D scattered data. <https://ch.mathworks.com/help/matlab/ref/griddata.html> (accessed 24 June 2022).
- Mena-Chalco, J.P., 2010. A fast voxel traversal algorithm for ray tracing, version 1.0.0.0. MATLAB Central File Exchange. <https://www.mathworks.com/matlabcentral/fileexchange/26852-a-fast-voxel-traversal-algorithm-for-ray-tracing>.
- Menzer, O., McFadden, J.P., 2017. Statistical partitioning of a three-year time series of direct urban net CO₂ flux measurements into biogenic and anthropogenic components. *Atmos. Environ.* 170, 319–333. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2017.09.049>.
- Moriwaki, R., Kanda, M., 2004. Seasonal and diurnal fluxes of radiation, heat, water vapor, and carbon dioxide over a suburban area. *J. Appl. Meteorol.* 43, 1700–1710. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JAM2153.1>.
- Oda, T., Maksyutov, S., Andres, R.J., 2018. The Open-source Data Inventory for Anthropogenic CO₂, version 2016 (ODIAC2016): a global monthly fossil fuel CO₂ gridded emissions data product for tracer transport simulations and surface flux inversions. *Earth Syst. Sci. Data* 10. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-10-87-2018>.
- OpenStreetMap, 2021. OpenStreetMap Foundation (OSMF). <https://www.openstreetmap.org/>.
- Peisker, M., Apel, H., 2001. Inhibition by light of CO₂ evolution from dark respiration: comparison of two gas exchange methods. *Photosynth. Res.* 70, 291–298. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1014799118368>.
- Santaren, D., Peylin, P., Viovy, N., Ciais, P., 2007. Optimizing a process-based ecosystem model with eddy-covariance flux measurements: a pine forest in southern France. *Glob. Biogeochem. Cycl.* 21. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2006GB002834>.
- Schulstandorte - Gemeinde Basel, 2021]. Grundbuch- und Vermessungsamt Kundenzentrum, Bau- und Verkehrsdepartement. https://www.geocat.ch/geonetwerk/srv/ger/md.viewer#/full_view/baf5ae32-de1d-411d-8fee-1c4de41cdf39.
- Spitters, C.J.T., 1986. Separating the diffuse and direct component of global radiation and its implications for modeling canopy photosynthesis Part II. Calculation of canopy photosynthesis. *Agric. For. Meteorol.* 38. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1923\(86\)90061-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1923(86)90061-4).
- Stagakis, S., Markos, N., Vanikiotis, T., Tzotsos, A., Sykioti, O., Kyparissis, A., 2015. SCASE: a primary productivity monitoring system for the forests of north pinus national park (epirus, greece). *Eur. J. Remote Sens.* 48. <https://doi.org/10.5772/EuJRS20154813>.
- Stagakis, S., Chrysoulakis, N., Spyridakis, N., Feigenwinter, C., Vogt, R., 2019. Eddy Covariance measurements and source partitioning of CO₂ emissions in an urban environment: application for Heraklion, Greece. *Atmos. Environ.* 201, 278–292. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2019.01.009>.
- Stagakis, S., Feigenwinter, C., Vogt, R., Kalberer, M., 2022. A high-resolution monitoring approach of urban CO₂ fluxes. Part 2 - Optimization framework using Eddy Covariance observations. Preprint available at <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4172740>.
- Stewart, I.D., Oke, T.R., 2012. Local climate zones for urban temperature studies. *Bull. Am. Meteorol. Soc.* 93, 1879–1900. <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-11-00019.1>.
- Strassen, Wege, 2022]. Amt für Mobilität Mobilitätsstrategie. https://www.geocat.ch/geonetwerk/srv/ger/md.viewer#/full_view/1854ab2e-7a1d-4a93-bc76-95add757283.
- Terrainmodell - DTM, 2022]. Grundbuch- und Vermessungsamt Amtliche Vermessung. https://www.geocat.ch/geonetwerk/srv/ger/md.viewer#/full_view/1bf94825-bd03-41a6-aefb-3dbe79fd0689.
- theia.download algorithm, 2021. https://github.com/olivierhagolle/theia_download (accessed 24 June 2022).
- Thornley, J.H.M., Johnson, I.R., 1990. *Plant and Crop Modelling: A Mathematical Approach to Plant and Crop Physiology*. Oxford University Press.
- Trotsiuk, V., Hartig, F., Cailleret, M., Babst, F., Forrester, D.I., Baltensweiler, A., Buchmann, N., Bugmann, H., Gessler, A., Garhau, M., Minunno, F., Rigling, A., Rohner, B., Stillhard, J., Thürrig, E., Waldner, P., Ferretti, M., Eugster, W., Schaub, M., 2020. Assessing the response of forest productivity to climate extremes in Switzerland using model–data fusion. *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 26, 2463–2476. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.15011>.
- UN, 2019. United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs. *World Urbanization Prospects: The 2018 Revision*. <https://doi.org/10.18356/b9e995fe-en> (accessed 24 June 2022).
- UNFCCC, 2015. The Paris Agreement, COP 21, Paris, 12 December 2015. <https://unfccc.int/process-and-meetings/the-paris-agreement/the-paris-agreement> (accessed 24 June 2022).
- Velasco, E., Roth, M., Norford, L., Molina, L.T., 2016. Does urban vegetation enhance carbon sequestration? *Landscape Urban Plan.* 148, 99–107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2015.12.003>.
- Verkehrsberechtigte Zonen, 2022]. Amt für Mobilität Mobilitätsstrategie. https://www.geocat.ch/geonetwerk/srv/ger/md.viewer#/full_view/9439aada-9c8a-4587-a1de-b0125b62a41f.
- Verkehrszählungen, 2022]. Amt für Mobilität Mobilitätsstrategie. https://www.geocat.ch/geonetwerk/srv/ger/md.viewer#/full_view/1631735b-e445-4d1-49121-92c9dbf2764e3.
- Verkehrszählungen motorisierter Individualverkehr, 2022. Amt für Mobilität, ID: 100006. <https://www.mobilitaet.bs.ch/gesamtverkehr/verkehrskennzahlen/verkehrszaehlung.html> accessed 24 June 2022.
- Villar, R., Held, A.A., Merino, J., 1995. Dark leaf respiration in light and darkness of an evergreen and a deciduous plant species. *Plant Physiol.* 107, 421–427. <https://doi.org/10.1104/pp.107.2.421>.
- Ward, H.C., Evans, J.G., Grimmond, C.S.B., 2013. Multi-season eddy covariance observations of energy, water and carbon fluxes over a suburban area in Swindon, UK. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.* 13, 4645–4666. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-13-4645-2013>.
- Weissert, L.F., Salmond, J.A., Turnbull, J.C., Schwendenmann, L., 2016. Temporal variability in the sources and fluxes of CO₂ in a residential area in an evergreen subtropical city. *Atmos. Environ.* 143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2016.08.044>.
- Winbourne, J.B., Smith, I.A., Stoyanova, H., Kohler, C., Gately, C.K., Logan, B.A., Reblin, J., Reinmann, A., Allen, D.W., Hutyra, L.R., 2022. Quantification of urban forest and grassland carbon fluxes using field measurements and a satellite-based model in Washington DC/Baltimore Area. *J. Geophys. Res. Biogeosciences* 127. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021JG006568>.
- Wohnbevölkerung, 2021]. Wohnbevölkerung nach Heimat und Block, ID: 100062. <https://www.basleratlas.ch/#c=home>.
- Wohnbevölkerung nach Alter und Arbeitspensum, 2022. <https://www.statistik.bs.ch/zahlen/tabellen/3-arbeit-erwerb/erwerb.html> (accessed 24 June 2022).
- Wu, K., Davis, K.J., Miles, N.L., Richardson, S.J., Lauvaux, T., Sarmiento, D.P., Balashov, N.V., Keller, K., Turnbull, J., Gurney, K.R., Liang, J., Roest, G., 2022. Source decomposition of eddy-covariance CO₂ flux measurements for evaluating a high-resolution urban CO₂ emissions inventory. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 17, 074035. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ac7c29>.
- Zhao, S., Liu, S., Zhou, D., 2016. Prevalent vegetation growth enhancement in urban environment. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 113. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1602312113>.
- Zhou, S., Duursma, R.A., Medlyn, B.E., Kelly, J.W.G., Prentice, I.C., 2013. How should we model plant responses to drought? An analysis of stomatal and non-stomatal responses to water stress. *Agric. For. Meteorol.* 182–183. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2013.05.009>.